

The effect of different carbon sources as an energy source for biological denitrification through *Pseudomonas stutzeri* and impact on other water quality parameters

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The results obtained in the present investigations of NO₃-N in the effluent was found to be lower than the tolerance limit 10 mg/L as NO₃-N prescribed by the WHO. Hence, when glucose was used as a carbon source at C/N ratio of 2.5, the organics started entering in the treated water. The sodium acetate is cheapest than other carbon sources. The present work provides a better alternate source of carbon for *in situ* denitrification through *Pseudomonas stutzeri*.

The higher concentration of nitrates were reported to cause disorders viz. Methaemoglobinemia, Cyanosis, Tumor and Goiter^{1,2}. Bacterial denitrification is identified as the assimilatory, biologically catalyzed reduction of nitrate and nitrite ions to form gaseous nitrogen and/or nitrogen oxides^{3,4}. The *Pseudomonas stutzeri* can use O₂, NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻ or nitrogen oxide as a terminal electron acceptor⁵. Heterotrophic denitrifying microorganisms can use a variety of organic carbon sources, such as methanol, sodium acetate, glucose, acetic acid and dimethyl sulphoxide^{6,7}. *Pseudomonas stutzeri* is an aerobic bacterium capable of using various carbon sources as substrate for denitrification under aerobic conditions that's why it can be used for *in situ* denitrification under such aerobics. The present study has been carried out the effect of different carbon sources on biological denitrification through *Pseudomonas stutzeri* and also finds out the impact on various water quality parameters.

Results and discussion

The observations of various water quality parameters at C/N ratios of 2.5 using different carbon sources in biological denitrification through *Pseudomonas stutzeri* has been given in Table 1. The process of denitrification was monitored using sodium acetate, glucose, methanol and dimethyl sulphoxide as carbon sources. The reactor was run for 15 days for acclimation without any monitoring. The all observations were taken and recorded after achieving pseudo-steady state in the *in situ* denitrification model with each carbon sources. The period of pseudo-steady state varied

from 11-14 days. The detailed observations for all the parameters were recorded everyday from day 11 to 16. The major observations and explanations are summarized in following paragraphs.

The Table 1 represents the values of different parameters vs time at C/N ratio of 2.5 using different carbon sources. The NO₃-N of the supplied water was contaminated by the mixing of KNO₃ to the tap water. The increased value of pH of the treated water indicates that the alkalinity generated during denitrification. The increased value of the alkalinity of the treated water confirm the generation of the alkalinity during denitrification. The influent COD varied between 381 to 381.6 mg/L and the effluent COD was ranged from 28.2 to 58.5 mg/L, which indicates that the carbon source (glucose) was not completely utilized during the biological denitrification process due to excess dose of carbon. The effluent nitrate-nitrogen was ranged from 0.47 to 2.03 mg/L, representing a removal efficiency of 98.4% using glucose as a carbon source. The influent COD was ranged from 246 to 266 mg/L and the effluent COD was nill under pseudo-steady state condition, which shows that the carbon source (sodium acetate) was completely utilized by the bacterium during denitrification. The observed values of the effluent NO₃-N were in a range between 0.57 to 2.33 mg/L representing a NO₃-N reduction efficiency of 97.5% using sodium acetate as a carbon source. The COD was ranged from 199 to 202 mg/L in the

Table 1. Values of different parameters vs time at C/N ratio 2.5 using different carbon sources

Day	Carbon source	Parameter										
		pH		Temp. °C	Alkalinity (mg/L)		DO (mg/L)		COD (mg/L)		NO ₃ -N (mg/L)	
		Influent	Effluent		Influent	Effluent	Influent	Effluent	Influent	Effluent	Influent	Effluent
11	Glucose	8.6	8.8	29.6	208	492	6.1	2.1	381.69	58.59	50.35	2.030
	Sodium acetate	8.4	8.8	24.8	488	576	6.3	2.1	246.0	0.0	51.53	2.158
	Methanol	8.5	8.7	31.2	140	420	6.3	2.0	199.77	0.0	51.53	1.8467
	Dimethyl sulphoxide	8.5	8.7	33.7	208	444	6.3	2.1	315.59	0.0	50.35	2.2462
12	Glucose	8.6	8.8	30.2	208	492	6.2	2.1	381.69	58.59	50.55	0.7281
	Sodium acetate	8.4	8.8	23.6	492	572	6.5	2.2	265.83	0.0	51.53	2.3376
	Methanol	8.5	8.7	31.5	140	420	6.2	2.0	200.80	0.0	50.93	1.4971
	Dimethyl sulphoxide	8.5	8.8	33.5	208	444	6.4	2.1	315.59	0.0	51.0	1.2964
13	Glucose	8.7	8.9	30.9	212	492	6.2	2.1	381.67	30.63	51.22	0.5383
	Sodium acetate	8.6	8.9	24.5	492	572	6.3	2.1	266.0	0.0	50.93	1.3751
	Methanol	8.4	8.6	33.3	192	432	6.2	2.1	200.80	0.0	51.0	1.3646
	Dimethyl sulphoxide	8.6	8.8	36.5	208	452	6.3	2.0	315.0	0.0	51.0	1.2960
14	Glucose	8.7	8.9	30.7	212	500	6.1	2.1	381.67	28.22	51.0	0.4746
	Sodium acetate	8.6	8.9	23.6	480	564	6.3	2.1	266.0	0.0	50.79	0.5704
	Methanol	8.5	8.7	34.2	192	432	6.3	2.1	199.03	0.0	50.82	1.3040
	Dimethyl sulphoxide	8.6	8.8	35.8	208	452	6.3	2.0	341.41	0.0	50.83	1.1035
15	Glucose	8.7	8.9	30.5	212	500	6.2	2.1	381.0	28.25	50.35	0.4746
	Sodium acetate	8.6	8.9	25.4	492	572	6.4	2.1	265.83	0.0	50.79	0.5704
	Methanol	8.5	8.7	34.8	192	432	6.3	2.1	202.0	0.0	50.0	1.3040
	Dimethyl sulphoxide	8.6	8.8	35.5	208	452	6.3	2.0	341.21	0.0	50.83	1.1030
16	Glucose	8.7	8.9	30.9	212	500	6.2	2.1	381.0	30.04	50.83	0.4746
	Sodium acetate	8.6	8.9	25.5	492	572	6.3	2.1	265.83	0.0	50.79	0.5704
	Methanol	8.5	8.8	35.8	192	432	6.3	2.1	202.0	0.0	50.0	1.3040
	Dimethyl sulphoxide	8.6	8.8	31.1	208	452	6.3	2.1	341.20	0.0	50.35	1.1030

influent and the effluent COD was nil under pseudo-steady state condition. The observed values of the NO₃-N were in a range between 1.3 to 1.8 mg/L representing a reduction efficiency of 97.1% using methanol as a carbon source. The influent COD varied between 315.5 to 341.4 mg/L. The effluent COD was nil under pseudo-steady state condition, which indicates that carbon source (dimethyl sulphoxide) was also completely utilized during denitrification at this C/N ratio. The observed values of the effluent NO₃-N were in a range between 1.1 to 2.2 mg/L representing a reduction in efficiency of 97.3% using dimethyl sulphoxide as a carbon source.

Conclusions and recommendations :

It could be concluded that the methanol, dimethyl sulphoxide and glucose as a carbon source provide to be equally efficient substrates for nitrate reduction in the ground water at C/N ratio of 2.5. When the sodium acetate was used as a carbon source the results were more or less similar to the results obtained with methanol, dimethyl sul-

phoxide and glucose. When glucose was used as a carbon source at C/N ratio of 2.5 the organics started entering in the treated water. It is recommended that the organics cannot be allowed in the potable water. The dosing quantity of above said carbon sources are similar. The cost comparison of different carbon sources shows that the sodium acetate is cheapest than other carbon sources. The operational convenience and marginal saving in cost, sodium acetate is a better solution than methanol, dimethyl sulphoxide and glucose.

Materials and methods :

Organism :

Pseudomonas stutzeri MTCC 101 was obtained from the culture collection laboratory, MTCC, Institute of Microbial Technology, Sector 39-A, Chandigarh, India.

Media :

The medium for the growth of *Pseudomonas stutzeri* contained beef extract, 1.0 g; yeast extract, 2.0 g; peptone, 5.0 g; NaCl, 5.0 g; agar, 15.0 g and distilled water, 1.0 L.

Incubation time was 48 h. Continuous cultures were made in chemo states fitted with dissolved oxygen and pH control. The temperature was maintained at 30°C and the pH at 56.9.

Experimental set-up and determination process :

A model was fabricated to simulate field conditions and start-up done by proper injecting of bacteria in it. The denitrification model was fabricated by placing two aluminum square brackets on two side of the model. The third bracket of the same size was placed at bottom in between the above placed brackets. Two parallel Perspex sheets were fixed on both sides of model. A rubber sheet was placed in between bracket and Perspex sheets so that model becomes water-tight. Three wells of plastic pipe wrapped with brass wire mesh and fixed at the bottom. Two wells were fixed at one end of the model out of which one well for serving as injection and another well for feed bacterial culture at the time of starting the reactor. The third well was fixed at the second end of the model for discharge. A tube was connected to discharge well with a provision to vary the head by placing it in a perforated and dimensionally marked pipe. The model was filled with water to check any leakages for one week. The model was filled with sand. The feeding reactor of 20 L capacity was used as feeding tank and 10 L capacity reactor was used as treated water collection. The model was initially run for two week with high nitrates tap water. The inflow and outflow contained same nitrate concentration after a brief initial period. Then the model was start-up with continuous flow of high-nitrated water and feed culture *Pseudomonas stutzeri* with liquid media. The reactor was run without monitoring until to achieve steady state condition. The influent and effluent samples were collected from the inlet and outlet wells. These samples were analyzed for various parameters using the standard procedure in accordance with the standard method of American Public Health Association (1995). Temperature was measured with thermometer; pH was measured by pH meter, alkalinity by titration. DO was measured by titration, COD was observed

by close reflux method using spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 600 nm and nitrate-nitrogen was measured by spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 220 nm. The instrument was used in the limit of precise accuracy and chemicals used were of analytical grade. The pH and temperature were recorded immediately at the sampling point. Samples for DO measurements were collected from the inlet tube and discharge tube at the bottom level and soon after DO was fixed in the bottle. Further, dissolved oxygen concentration in samples was measured in laboratory by Winkler's method. The supplied water was made high nitrated using potassium nitrate to the tap water and also mixed one among of these substrate; sodium acetate, glucose, methanol and dimethyl sulphoxide in supplied water for carbon source^{8,9}.

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